

Barriers to perform research studies from the perspective of medical students of Khyber Medical College Peshawar

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Abstract

Introduction: The pursuit of medical research is a cornerstone of scientific progress and contributes to the development of healthcare systems. Despite the well-known benefits of involving medical students in research, barriers and challenges often hinder their active participation.

Objective: This study investigates the barriers hindering medical students at Khyber Medical College, Peshawar, in their pursuit of research opportunities, with the aim of facilitating a more research-oriented environment that enhances their scholarly output and contributes to the broader field of healthcare.

Methods And Materials: A descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted from 30th May to 30th August involving 264 medical students of 3rd to 5th-year MBBS (Participants) currently enrolled in Khyber Medical College, Peshawar (Setting). Intervention: The data was collected through a self-administered, validated questionnaire. SPSS version 27.0 was used for analysing the data. One sample t-test and ANOVA were used to describe the association between variables. P value <0.05 was considered statistically significant. The primary outcome measure was the mean score of barriers from the Likert scale used in the questionnaire. A comparison of different categories of barriers was also done as a part of a secondary outcome measure.

Results: The study revealed that medical students at Khyber Medical College encounter significant barriers to research, with an overall mean score of 3.9110 ± 0.4645 . The most significant barriers were the failure to allocate sufficient funds 4.37 ± 0.764 and the absence of a research-oriented culture in society 4.34 ± 0.794 . Conversely, the least prominent barriers were a lack of proficiency in English 3.09 ± 1.248 , and inadequate facilities 3.38 ± 1.357 .

Conclusion: This study sheds light on the challenges faced by medical students in pursuing research at Khyber Medical College, Peshawar. Addressing these barriers is essential for enhancing the research culture, educational excellence, and healthcare outcomes.

Keywords: biomedical research, delivery of health care, education, medical, undergraduate.

1. INTRODUCTION

Throughout human history, a key belief held by individuals is the reliance on evidence to support their beliefs. In tandem with education and modernization, this trend has consistently been on the rise. Medical research provides the needed evidence that plays a vital role in enhancing our understanding of diseases, expanding diagnostic possibilities, exploring potential treatments, and preventing illnesses¹. The knowledge in the field of medicine is not definitive and is continually evolving with new research findings². In contemporary times it is crucial to divide this work equally amongst all sectors of healthcare professionals including medical students. However, studies have shown otherwise with residents and faculty conducting the bulk of the research work³.

Research stimulates critical thinking, reasoning, and problem-solving attitudes. It is a way of expressing interest that nurtures creative and innovative minds and brings up teamwork, especially

during the early education of medical students⁴. These qualities form the foundation for developing into skilled physicians who can deliver healthcare effectively to the patients⁵. Evidence suggests that undergraduate students who engage in research and subsequently publish articles demonstrate a significant increase almost three-fold, in their scholarly output as medical professionals⁶. Also participating in research while in medical school helps in exploring and finding academic interests that favourably impact the decision of medical students regarding their academic career choice⁷.

Despite well-known advantages and benefits, there is still a limited amount of literature work done among medical students. Especially in developing countries where the situation is in a more dire situation for many reasons that are different, unique, and more in number than the developed world. South Asia contributes a mere 1.2% to global research output, with Pakistan facing even more alarming circumstances with an alarming declining rate of

physician-scientists because of its shortage of academically oriented physician-scientists⁵. Pakistan, with its significant population, ranks as the fifth most populous nation globally after China, India, the United States, and Indonesia⁹. Pakistan with its substantial population, has the potential to make a valuable contribution to global medical literature. Also, Pakistan requires its own distinct literary works to address the unique ailments that afflict its population, distinguishing it from other countries.

The early exposure of medical students to their educational curriculum can yield numerous advantages in the future. In our study, we aim to identify barriers that are still deterring them from pursuing research and reaping the intended advantages. A study conducted by Jai Kumar et al in Pakistan shows major barriers to medical students conducting research are lack of knowledge followed by lack of time, lack of mentoring, lack of finances, and others⁵.

Another study carried out in Pakistan revealed that insufficient funding was the primary barrier, followed by a prioritizing educational curriculum over research, lack of knowledge and skills, and lack of incentive¹⁰. A study conducted in a private college in Lahore showed excessive curriculum workload, exhaustion, and burnout leading factors limiting students from participating in research¹¹. The findings of a study conducted at Rehman Medical College in Pakistan indicate that the majority of students are not provided with sufficient opportunities to present and publish their research work with an extensive demanding curriculum and the fear of exams being major obstacles¹².

In the realm of medical research and the pursuit of knowledge, several studies conducted internationally have delved into the motivations and barriers faced by both medical students and also primary care physicians. These investigations shed light on the critical factors influencing research participation and the hurdles that impede such engagement.

A very thorough study conducted by Hasan Ashrafi et al from Isfahan University of Medical Sciences, determined that overall mean of barriers was 3.89 ± 0.483 . Foremost barrier was attributed to density of student's curriculum, and then to lack of familiarity with method of research. Least perceived barrier was lack of access to suitable library resources. His esteemed study also categorizes the barriers showing individual barriers being most significant.¹³

A study conducted by Al Habib et al in Saudi Arabia focused on the motivations and barriers encountered by medical students. Notably, the barriers with the most substantial impact were identified as "lack of time," cited by 29.2% of participants, "lack of monitoring," reported by 16.8%, and "lack of interest in research," expressed by 14.7% of respondents.¹⁴

Furthermore, Khalaf AJ's investigation on primary care physicians in contrast to attitudes and barriers towards research, published in BMC Family Practice, brought to the forefront the multifaceted challenges they face. Participants in this study identified several key barriers, with insufficient research time allocation ranking highest at 76.5%, followed by issues such as insufficient financial support (63%), lack of financial incentives (51%), and inadequate statistical support (50%).¹⁵ Interestingly, the study also revealed significant

associations between barriers and physicians' designations and specialty board certificates.

In a study by J. Kumar et al. in Liaquat University of Health Sciences Karachi, the barriers to research participation among medical students were examined. The findings unveiled that a substantial majority, approximately 90.68% of the participants, identified "lack of knowledge" as a formidable barrier. Following closely were "lack of time," with 88.79% of respondents acknowledging its hindrance, and "lack of mentoring," identified as the third most common obstacle, with 85.74% of participants recognizing its impact.⁵

Additionally, a study conducted at King Khalid University in Abha, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, pinpointed critical barriers to research engagement. The study highlighted that "lack of skills" emerged as the most significant impediment, closely followed by "lack of time" and a shortage of statistical proficiency. Interestingly, the study found that difficulties in report writing and data collection were among the least formidable barriers faced by researchers.

These studies collectively underscore the intricate landscape of research participation in the undergraduate medical community, shedding light on both the motivations that drive individuals to engage in research and the multifaceted barriers that they must contend with.¹⁶ Understanding these dynamics is critical for devising strategies to foster a culture of research and innovation in the field of medicine specially at student level.

This research endeavours to undertake a comprehensive investigation into the impediments faced by medical students at Khyber Medical College, Peshawar, in their pursuit of research studies. Acknowledging these barriers is paramount for multifaceted reasons. First, it fosters educational excellence by cultivating critical thinking and evidence-based practice.

Second, it contributes to the advancement of medical science and innovation, thereby enhancing patient care. Third, it cultivates the career development of aspiring healthcare professionals, granting them a competitive edge. Lastly, this inquiry empowers the institution by providing insights for tailored support mechanisms, thus augmenting college's academic eminence and its stature in the medical community.

2. MATERIAL AND METHODS

Study Design:

A descriptive cross-sectional study was performed from 30th May to 30th August, 2023. The ethical approval was taken from the Institutional Research and Ethics Review Board (IREB) of Khyber Medical College (KMC), Peshawar on 18th May, 2023 (DME/KMC # 292, Date: 18-05-2023).

Study population and Sample size:

The study population consisted of the students of 3rd year to 5th year MBBS currently enrolled in KMC, which were a total of 850 students. The sample size based on Krejcie and Morgan's table came out to be 265.

Study setting and Sampling technique:

The study was performed at KMC with 3rd Year to 5th Year medical students as respondents. The respondents were selected through a non-probability convenience sampling technique.

Data collection:

Data was collected using a self-administered questionnaire. The questionnaire used was a previously validated questionnaire adopted from an already-published study by Hasan Asharfi-rizi et al (2015). The questionnaire was used after obtaining permission from the author. The questionnaire was developed based on the research findings of many previous studies and an extensive literature review. The questionnaire was distributed via Google Forms. An informed consent was obtained and the respondents were ensured confidentiality.

The questionnaire consisted of two sections. The first section was about general demographics including year of study and gender. The second section consisted of 50 items related to research barriers divided into four categories.

The first category was related to organizational barriers (1-29 Q), the second category to cultural and social barriers (30-35 Q), the third category was to individual barriers (36-46 Q), and the fourth category was related to economic barriers (47-50 Q). A 5-point Likert scale (strongly agree, agree neutral, disagree and strongly disagree) was designed to collect the responses.

In this study, strongly agree was scored 5, agree 4, neutral 3, disagree 2 and strongly disagree 1. The questionnaire was tested through a pilot study on 30 students (10% of the sample size) from the target population. The reliability and internal consistency of the questionnaire were confirmed using Cronbach's alpha which came out to be 0.70.

Data Analysis:

After data collection, data was organized, coded, and tabulated using SPSS version 27.0. The descriptive statistics (frequency, percentages, mean and standard deviation) for all the variables were obtained. Inferential statistics including one sample t-test and ANOVA were used to describe the association between variables. P value <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

3. Results

The study was done to find out barriers faced in performing research studies from perspective of undergraduate medical students reaching clinical years of study (3rd year to Final Year) of Khyber Medical College, Peshawar. Demographics were 179 (67.8%) males and 85 (32.2%) females from total sample of 264 as shown in table 1.1.

Students participated belonged to 3rd, 4th and Final Year MBBS with percentage of 14.8%, 9.5% and 75.8% respectively as shown in table 1.2.

Results showed that the overall mean of barriers during research activities among students of Khyber Medical College, Peshawar was 3.9110 ± 0.4645 .

The highest mean was related to Failure to allocate sufficient funds for student research (4.37 ± 0.764) followed by Lack of Research Culture in our society (4.34 ± 0.794), lack of Seriousness about student's research activities (4.30 ± 0.768) Lack of systematic research cores for students in Schools (4.20 ± 0.802), Unfamiliarity with the acceptance criteria and published articles in various journals (4.20 ± 0.773) and, lowest mean respectively related to Lack of proficiency in English (3.09 ± 1.248), Not selected students' researchers rightfully (3.31 ± 0.937) and Lack of facilities and equipment (computers etc.) (3.38 ± 1.357) Table 2.1.

Also, the mean of research activities's barriers, according to dimensions showed that the mean in Economical dimension (4.0142 ± 0.692) was more than dimensions: Social and cultural dimensions (3.9192 ± 0.620), Organizational barriers (3.8598 ± 0.809) and Individual barriers level (3.8509 ± 0.660). The lowest mean was related to Individual barriers Table 2.2.

One sample t-test was performed to find out if there is any Statistical difference between a mean and a known or hypothesized value of the mean in the population and was statistically significant. Table 2.3.

Data Statement:

Technical appendix, statistical code, and dataset available from the repository, DOI Data Repository - Google Drive.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Female	85	32.2	32.2	32.2
	Male	179	67.8	67.8	100.0
	Total	264	100.0	100.0	

Table 1. Gender

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	3rd Year	39	14.8	14.8	14.8
	4th Year	25	9.5	9.5	24.2
	Final Year	200	75.8	75.8	100.0

Total	264	100.0	100.0	
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Table 2. Year of Study in Medical School

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Lack of access to counsel and appropriate guide in research	264	1	5	4.00	1.115
Cumbersome regulatory and acceptance criteria of publishing article in journals	264	2	5	4.09	.851
Not enough incentives (promotion, recognition etc)	264	2	5	4.05	.828
Failing to account research activities in the students' final grades	264	1	5	3.54	1.156
Lack of access to adequate library resources	264	1	5	3.50	1.196
Lack of cooperation of organization in conducting research	264	2	5	3.99	.992
Lack of awareness to institutional research priorities	264	2	5	4.01	.859
Not selected student researcher rightfully	264	1	5	3.31	.937
Not familiar with the organizational rules and regulations carried out in research	264	1	5	3.59	1.013
Lack of appropriate allocation of credit in accordance with the principles of research in university courses	264	1	5	3.70	.958
Unwillingness of faculty to work with student in research activities	264	1	5	3.40	1.244
Lack of facilities and equipment necessary to do research (computers, printers,)	264	1	5	3.38	1.357
Time limits for research	264	1	5	3.48	1.071
Expect to get positive result from research	264	1	5	3.81	.895
Nonimpact of research activity in the employment of bureaucracy	264	1	5	3.42	1.007
Lack of constraint in doing research activities for students	264	1	5	3.52	.975
Lack of systematic research cores for students in Schools	261	3	5	4.20	.602
Lack Seriousness about student's research activities.	264	2	5	4.30	.768
Lengthy process of review and approval of research projects	264	2	5	3.83	1.002
Lack of professional librarians to guide the use of resources	264	1	5	4.06	.940
Inequality in the adoption and implementation of student research projects to other researchers	264	1	5	3.75	1.016
Density of the students' curriculum	264	2	5	4.14	1.005
Not having adequate education for participation in congresses and seminars	264	1	5	3.87	1.097
Not using of result by organizations	264	2	5	3.76	.882
Lack of dynamism and efficiency of the education system.	264	2	5	4.08	.766
No impact of the research activities in admission of students in the higher education sectors.	264	1	5	3.45	1.213
Difficult to accept student papers in academic journals.	264	2	5	3.98	.885
Difficult to accept student papers at national and regional seminars	264	1	5	3.74	.952
The lack of research culture in society	264	2	5	4.34	.794
No proper place in society for research	264	1	5	3.84	1.074
Not effect of the results of research activities in public life	264	1	5	3.89	.990
Not counting the researcher as a business in society	264	1	5	3.92	.968
No need of people to research results	264	1	5	3.45	1.038

Lack of appropriate scientific and research space	264	1	5	4.06	.935
Lack of interest or motivation to do research	264	1	5	3.80	1.215
Lack of proficiency in English	264	1	5	3.09	1.248
Lack of sufficient familiarity with research methods	264	1	5	4.00	1.091
Not adequate familiarity with statistics	264	1	5	4.09	.937
Lack of time and a lot of concern (family and community)	264	1	5	3.88	1.088
Unfamiliarity with the help of other researchers carrying out their research	264	1	5	3.85	.802
Lack of information about the search and evaluation of online library materials	264	1	5	3.72	1.039
Inability to recognize areas of research	264	1	5	3.86	1.058
Force to use a special framework and method of research (e.g., methods, tools,)	264	1	5	3.69	1.003
Insufficient experience in research	264	1	5	4.18	.999
Unfamiliarity with the acceptance criteria and published articles in various journals	264	2	5	4.20	.773
Failure to allocate sufficient funds for student research	264	2	5	4.37	.764
The lack of cost-effective of research activities to other activities	264	2	5	4.03	.843
Lack of timely payment of fees for research.	264	2	5	3.97	.908
Differentiate between the fees of students to faculty	264	2	5	3.69	.873
Valid N (listwise)	261				

Table 3. Mean and Standard deviation of Individual Barrier

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Organizational barriers	264	2.00	5.00	3.8598	.80944
Society and cultural barriers	264	2.17	5.00	3.9192	.62072
Individual barriers	264	1.73	5.00	3.8509	.66021
Economical barriers	264	2.25	5.00	4.0142	.69219
Valid N (listwise)	264				

Table 4. Mean of Categories of Barriers Descriptive Statistics

	Test Value = 3					
	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
					Lower	Upper
Organizational barriers	17.260	263	.000	.85985	.7618	.9579
Society and cultural barriers	24.061	263	.000	.91919	.8440	.9944
Individual barriers	20.941	263	.000	.85090	.7709	.9309
Economical barriers	23.807	263	.000	1.01420	.9303	1.0981
Overall Mean	31.863	263	.000	.91104	.8547	.9673

Table 5. One Sample T-test

4. DISCUSSION

The progress of a nation is closely linked to scientific and technological research. Consequently, it is crucial to establish a well-structured and focused framework for the development of the country's research system.

However, a key initial stride in creating an efficient and comprehensive framework involves inspiring educators, researchers, and particularly students to engage in research activities and removing any obstacles that hinder research endeavors.¹⁷

The involvement of medical students in research, their training and mentorship for smooth conduction of research, and their problems along with solutions especially in Pakistan have not been adequately addressed by an appropriate number of studies.¹⁰

Our study serves the vital purpose of shedding light on the significant issue of reduced participation in research among undergraduate medical students at Khyber Medical College, Peshawar. This study encompasses a substantial sample size of 264 participants, consisting of 67.8% males and 32.2% females, with the majority in their final year (75.8%). Our findings indicate that, on average, students encountered moderate barriers while engaging in research activities, with an overall mean score of 3.9110 ± 0.4645 . This mean score closely aligns with the value calculated in a separate study at Isfahan University of Medical Sciences, which was 3.89 ± 0.483 .¹³

While undergraduate students typically hold a favourable view of research, their practical knowledge and engagement in research activities tend to be limited. It is imperative to implement substantial measures aimed at elevating the level of research knowledge and hands-on experience among undergraduate students.¹⁸

Furthermore, the most significant mean barrier was attributed to the failure to allocate sufficient funds, followed by the absence of a research-oriented culture in our society. This finding aligns with a study conducted by Bilal et al in Karachi, which identified the lack of funding support and a preference for instructional activities over research as the most noteworthy obstacles.¹⁰ This may be attributed to economic instability and sociopolitical affairs of institutions in our county.

Conversely, research conducted at a private college in Lahore has revealed that an excessive curriculum load, fatigue, and burnout are the primary factors deterring students from actively participating in research opportunities¹¹. Similarly, a study carried out at Rehman Medical College by Fazia et al has highlighted that a substantial number of students lack adequate opportunities to showcase and publish their research endeavors. These impediments are largely attributed to the demanding curriculum and the anxiety associated with exams¹².

Another study conducted by Hasan Ashrafi et al from Isfahan University of Medical Sciences and RMC, led by Fazia Raza, identified the density of students' curriculum as the foremost barrier, closely followed by a lack of familiarity with research methods¹³. In addition, Al Habib et al in Saudi Arabia emphasized that a lack of time is the most prominent barrier¹⁴.

Notably, a study by J. Kumar at Liaquat University of Health Sciences in Karachi highlighted that a lack of knowledge was the leading barrier⁵. On the other hand, research by King Khalid University in Abha, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, pinpointed a lack of skills as the primary barrier.¹⁶

Conversely, the least perceived barriers were a lack of proficiency in English, followed by a lack of facilities, which aligns with a study by Hassan Ashrafi indicating that limited access to libraries was the least prominent barrier. This also corresponds with research conducted by Al-habib et al, which emphasized that limited access to databases had the least impact on research endeavors¹⁴. Furthermore, Fazia et al also identified a lack of interest as the least significant barrier¹².

Differences in research outcomes across studies can be attributed to numerous factors. These include variations in research context, sample demographics, socioeconomic conditions, and temporal changes. Cultural distinctions, research design, biases, geographic factors, institutional policies, and data collection methods also play significant roles. These variations enrich scientific understanding by highlighting the complex interplay of variables. They are helpful to comprehend diverse outcomes, emphasizing the dynamic and context-dependent nature of research. These disparities underscore the importance of tailoring research to specific environments and acknowledging that they contribute to a more comprehensive body of knowledge.

Identification of these calls for a need to restructure the medical curriculum and start educating the medical students in their early years about the basics of research and its importance so that they are better able to participate and contribute to the research well in time during their academic years. This measure has been supported by a qualitative study that proved a positive change in the student's perceptions after undertaking a research course study¹⁹. Mandatory participation of the students as part of their examination system has also brought about positive results²⁰.

believe it's important for enhancing critical thinking and formulating health policies which eventually led to making well-appreciated improvements in both educational and practical fields. Purushottam A Giri et al. stated that 91.4% of the students believed that patient outcome improves with continued medical research.²¹

Article Summary

Strengths and Limitations:

- To the best of our knowledge, this study is the first of its kind on this topic originating from Khyber Medical College, Peshawar. We had a fully developed questionnaire, validated.
- It used a self-administered questionnaire.
- This was a cross-sectional study using survey data with a small sample size; therefore, only limited generalizability of these findings can be claimed.
- Students from only one College were the study subjects, so future research will have to be a multi-city design to assess the extent to which it is possible to generalize the results of this study to cover all medical colleges.

Conclusion and Recommendations:

In conclusion, this study provides valuable insights into the barriers faced by undergraduate medical students during research activities, offering a foundation for addressing these challenges and fostering a more research-friendly environment within the institution and society. Future research and interventions can build upon these findings to further enhance the research experience for students.

The key recommendations for improving student research in educational institutions are as follows:

- **Funding Support:** Educational institutions should create grants, scholarships, and research fellowships to provide financial resources for student research.
- **Promoting a Research Culture:** Cultivate a research-oriented culture through research seminars, workshops, and mentorship programs to guide students.

- **Enhancing Seriousness:** Encourage students to take research seriously and involve faculty to enhance research outcomes.
- **Establishing Research Cores:** Create systematic research cores within institutions to provide students with necessary infrastructure and support for effective research.
- **Publication Guidance:** Offer guidance on journal acceptance criteria and the publication process to improve the quality of student research output.
- **Economic Support:** Explore ways to alleviate economic barriers that hinder students' engagement in research.

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Conflict of Interest: None

Author Contributions:

Conceived and designed the analysis: Muhammad Zohaib Rehman, Junaid Imran

Collected the data: Malek Shehryar, Abdullah Wahdan Yahya

Contributed data or analysis tools: Abdullah Wahdan Yahya, Muhammad Zohaib Rehman,

Malik Shehryar.

Performed the analysis: Junaid Imran, Muhammad Zohaib Rehman

Wrote the paper: Muhammad Zohaib Rehman, Junaid Imran, Malik Shehryar, Abdullah Wahdan Yahya.

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